

Skills for the **curation of sensitive data**

HDRUK
Health Data Research UK

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About HDR UK

Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) is accelerating trustworthy use of health data to enable discoveries that improve people's lives. We are the national institute for health data science. Our vision is for large-scale data to benefit every interaction with patients, every clinical trial and every biomedical discovery, and to transform public health.

HDR UK is an independent, registered charity with five years of core funding from nine of the UK's leading medical research funders, including UK Research and Innovation, the Department of Health and Social Care in England and equivalents in Northern Ireland, Wales and Scotland, and leading medical research charities.

About SSI

The Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) was the first organisation in the world dedicated to improving software in research. It was founded in 2010 on the premise that helping individuals and institutions to understand the vital role that software plays in research would accelerate progress in every field of scientific and academic endeavour. The SSI has set itself the ambitious goal of transforming academic culture by establishing the principle that reliable, reproducible, and reusable software is necessary across all research disciplines. Recently, the SSI has moved into policy research, focusing on skills, careers and infrastructure in academia and industry.

Statement of funding

This project has received funding through the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Programme.

Executive summary

Secure access to sensitive data through Trusted Research Environments (TREs)¹ is a powerful enabler of research with vast potential for public benefit, and access to sensitive datasets that are linked together provides an even more powerful research tool. The ability to harness this power hinges on a critical, yet often underestimated, step: data curation. Data curation encompasses a range of actions (including data cleaning, data transformation, metadata creation, and documentation) undertaken to ensure that data are understood and usable. It is a highly skilled technical role that requires a multidisciplinary team. However, there is a growing data curation skills gap across digital research infrastructures that risks creating barriers to research. This risk is compounded for sensitive data where hands-on skills development requires access to secure digital research infrastructure.

As the secure use of sensitive data in research continues to expand², so does the need for a well-defined and well-supported professional workforce capable of preparing and managing data in secure environments. In support of this, the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Programme funded this project to identify skills that could be prioritised for training, and to understand how best to deliver such training in a way that responds to the needs and constraints of those who curate sensitive data. To meet this objective, the study engaged with the sector through key informant interviews, a UK-wide survey, and three focus groups, generating a rich picture of current practice, skills gaps, and training challenges.

Across interviews, surveys, and focus groups with data curators, TRE/SDE/Safe Haven operators, governance specialists, and training providers, a clear picture emerges: there is both an opportunity and need for skills development, and strong appetite for structured training and career pathways. The majority of survey respondents (64%) reported that strengthening data curation skills would positively impact their career development, and most (74%) expressed interest in a skills framework or professional pathway. In short, there is a motivated and engaged community where targeted support can add tangible value.

Yet, the current training landscape is patchy. Only around 5% of respondents reported full training in data curation, with most relying on informal learning, self-guided online resources, or in-house provision. Formal training is more common in early-career roles, tapering off as responsibilities grow, and is often

¹ Also called, and including for the purposes of this report, Secure Data Environments and Safe Havens

² https://dareuk.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/2310_DARE_UK_DigInfraLandscapeReview_Final.pdf

constrained by limited time or lack of suitable courses. Participants described the landscape as confusing, with “too much choice and not enough choice at the same time” and noted the absence of a recognised skills framework as a barrier to planning and articulating development needs.

Participants identified a mix of technical and professional competencies as critical to sensitive data curation, including knowledge of legal obligations, understanding anonymisation processes, the ability to conduct disclosure checks, interpreting data in context, and domain knowledge. Early-career participants highlighted governance and legal knowledge, while more experienced respondents focused on practical application.

TRE literacy consistently emerged as a key skills gap across all career stages and was identified as broadly transferable across roles and settings. Additional gaps included knowledge of legal obligations and the ability to structure data curation work so that it is reproducible, transparent, and reusable.

Overall, the findings highlight opportunities to strengthen how skills are defined, developed, and embedded across the sector.

These findings point to several priority areas for action.

Priority areas for action

Building on the evidence, we have identified our next actions to pilot, refine, and scale skills development in sensitive data curation. These are designed to make training accessible, relevant, and aligned with organisational and sector-wide priorities:

1. **Develop and pilot a foundational TRE Literacy curriculum**

The cross-discipline TRE Literacy curriculum will embed high-priority skills (including legal obligations and emerging AI considerations) within applied learning, with scope for local adaptation and role-specific pathways.

2. **Design training for wide accessibility**

The curriculum and accompanying Train the Trainer programme will use a flipped classroom model, combining self-led online modules with in-person workshops, providing flexibility while supporting peer interaction and applied learning.

3. **Align training with organisational processes**

Partner with organisations to integrate sensitive data curation skills development into appraisal processes, role design, and career pathways, supporting protected time for professional development.

4. **Support existing skills frameworks by integrating evidence on sensitive data curation skills**

Enhancing granularity within established frameworks helps staff and employers identify gaps, select appropriate training, and recognise professional boundaries.

5. **Improve sector-wide connectivity and visibility of skills development activity**

Convene stakeholders across the sensitive data skills and career landscape to strengthen knowledge exchange, surface existing training and communities of practice, and align future priorities, including via an in-person Skills Summit.

Progress will require coordinated, sector-wide effort, with shared responsibility across training providers and skills organisations, TRE/SDE/Safe Haven operators and host organisations, funders, data and information governance bodies, and data curators and professional communities rather than reliance on any single initiative.

The accompanying [recommendations for key stakeholders](#) set out a roadmap to improve skills and strengthen recognition in sensitive data curation.

Detailed findings

Defining ‘data curation’ and ‘sensitive data’

Within this still nascent profession, there are no clear-cut definitions of data curation, ‘sensitive’ data, or what constitutes the curation of sensitive data. To help us characterise these so that we can focus our training on the skills required for the curation of sensitive data specifically, we asked interview, survey, and focus group participants to define what is involved in data curation generally, and what is unique or most important in the curation of sensitive data.

First, our key informant interview participants were asked for their definitions. This led us to a working definition of data curation as:

The process of managing and preparing data so that it is accurate, well-documented, and suitable for analysis – often described as making data “research-ready” or “analysis-ready”. This may involve cleaning, transforming, integrating, documenting, and safeguarding data throughout its lifecycle.

We also developed a working definition of sensitive data, building on definitions from NHS England, DARE UK, EOSC Entrust and the Information Commissioners Office, which was:

Sensitive data refers to confidential information that, if disclosed or accessed without authorisation, could lead to harm or adverse consequences for individuals. This includes personal data such as health information and other special category data as in GDPR, but also individual's financial details, or commercially sensitive data. We also include any data stored or processed within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE). A TRE is any digital system—or group of systems—designed to securely manage sensitive research data. Other terms for these environments include Secure Data Environment (SDE), data safe haven, and similar. Examples of sensitive data typically managed in these environments include genomic or genetic data, medical imaging and electronic health records, commercial or financial data, administrative data (e.g. tax, benefits, or social care), education data (e.g. school or university records), and more.

These working definitions were provided to survey respondents to help frame their answers to questions about data curation and the curation of sensitive data. We caveated these definitions by stating that we recognised that data curation is a complex and evolving practice, and definitions may vary across contexts.

Further refining our definitions, we asked respondents to indicate which aspects of the curation of sensitive data are distinct from general data curation. In addition, when we asked about skills (more analysis below), we asked what skills were unique to, or particularly important in, sensitive data curation.

These definitions and survey findings have enabled us to better define what the curation of sensitive data entails and how it is distinct from general data curation. As such, we are able to focus our decision making regarding the skills that our training will focus on.

(Numbers displayed refer to response counts; See appendix 1.1)

Are any of these skills unique, or particularly important in, sensitive data curation?

(Numbers displayed refer to response counts; See appendix 1.2)

Who curates sensitive data?

Our survey questions allowed us to understand the different people who curate sensitive data.

Questions about years of experience, career stage, and the list of responsibilities (developed from the key informant interviews) showed us the range of people who responded. ([Appendix 1.3](#), [1.4](#), [1.5](#))

Respondents predominantly work with health data, with 93% currently using this data type, while only 9% work with commercial data. Most participants work across two to three data types, reflecting interdisciplinary data practice, and the majority are based within academic institutions. This profile aligns with findings from the [UK Sensitive Data Research Infrastructure: A Landscape Review](#), which identifies health data as the most common domain (85%) and universities as a key institutional base (41%) for sensitive data research infrastructure.

The cohort also reflects a highly multi-functional workforce. Roles are concentrated in research and data service functions, with fewer in senior leadership positions, and individuals typically undertake a wide range of responsibilities. The most common activities combine technical and professional skills such as liaising with researchers, transferring and cleaning data, and quality assurance alongside project management and coordination with data providers. Overall, this highlights the breadth and diversity of curation roles, which vary across workplaces and contexts, making them less easily standardised or targeted.

As one might expect, those early in their career did more day-to-day process tasks such as transferring data, cleaning data, and liaising with researchers. Mid-career respondents had more project management and decision-making responsibilities, while those with more experience/ later career stage had more strategic and people management responsibilities. This range of duties, and the skills they require, already indicate the complexity of the skills landscape we are looking to understand.

| Established Career |
|---|--|--|
| <p>Top 5 Responsibilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transferring data Liaising with researchers and/or other clients Liaising with organisations involved with the data source Data cleaning Quality assurance checks | <p>Top 5 Responsibilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liaising with researchers and/or other clients Managing projects Making decisions on how to handle data (e.g., free text or image data) Gathering or producing documentation of data curation process Transferring data | <p>Top 5 Responsibilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transferring data Liaising with researchers and/or other clients Managing projects Managing a team Making decisions on how to handle data (e.g., free text or image data) |
| <p>What are your responsibilities? Full List:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arranging data sharing agreements Creating extracts of data (for researchers within a TRE/SDE) Data acquisition Data cleaning Data minimisation De-identifying, pseudonymisation, and anonymising data Dealing with data protection incidents and breaches Disclosure checking (input and output checking) Ensuring adherence to organisational standards (e.g., ISO27001) Gaining information governance approvals Gathering or producing documentation of data curation process Gathering or producing metadata Information governance Liaising with organisations involved with the data source Liaising with researchers and/or other clients Linking data Making decisions on how to handle data (e.g., free text or image data) Making decisions on strategy for a TRE/SDE Managing projects Managing a team Quality assurance checks Requirements gathering Research and clinical activity Strategic or senior management Transferring data | | |

(See appendix 1.6, 1.7, 1.8 for full breakdown.)

The skills required to curate data, and sensitive data

When looking to understand the skills required for data curation and the curation of sensitive data, we first asked our key informants for their perspectives, which we consolidated into a list of 42 skills grouped broadly into technical skills (expertise and understanding; governance and compliance; preparation, analysis and advanced techniques; management and documentation; and working with data) and professional skills (working with clients/customers; communication; cognition; organisation; and working with colleagues).

In your experience, what skills are required for doing data curation work?

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix 1.9)

We then asked, of the skills selected, which were the top 5 most important for their role, and which skills were unique to or particularly important in, the curation of sensitive data.

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix [1.10](#), [1.11](#))

These plots show that while professional skills are widely used, the skills that are considered most important are weighted more towards technical skills, and the top five skills specific to the curation of sensitive data are all technical skills.

To understand the skills needed by different people, we broke the responses down by career stage.

Are any of these skills unique to, or particularly important in, sensitive data curation?
Broken down by career stage:

| Established Career |
|---|--|--|
| <p>Top 5 responses (number of responses)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding of anonymisation processes (6) Knowledge of legal obligations (e.g., GDPR, disclosure control) (6) Understanding of how terminology is used within a certain context (4) Understanding of TRE/SDE infrastructure literacy (4) Confidence to question data when it does not look right (4) Ability to problem-solve (4) Ability to do disclosure checks (also known as output checking) (4) Ability to create metadata (e.g. a data dictionary) (4) | <p>Top 5 responses (number of responses)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of legal obligations (e.g., GDPR, disclosure control) (19) Understanding of anonymisation processes (14) Awareness of and ability to interpret data within its external and contextual influences (9) Ability to do disclosure checks (also known as output checking) (9) Domain knowledge (8) | <p>Top 5 responses (number of responses)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding of anonymisation processes (13) Knowledge of legal obligations (e.g., GDPR, disclosure control) (13) Ability to do disclosure checks (also known as output checking) (9) Awareness of and ability to interpret data within its external and contextual influences (7) Domain knowledge (5) Confidence to question data when it does not look right (5) Ability to adapt to diverse data sources, formats, and types — including working with linked data (5) |

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix [1.12](#), [1.13](#), [1.14](#))

This breakdown indicates that for the top five most commonly cited skills, **understanding anonymisation processes** and **knowledge of legal obligations** are common across career stages. **Ability to do disclosure checks**, **domain knowledge**, and the **ability to interpret data in context** were shared by those in mid-career and those with more established careers.

Thinking about yourself, select up to five skills you feel least well-equipped with for your current role.

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix 1.15)

Skill gaps

Next, survey participants were asked about the five skills they felt least well equipped in.

Of these, **knowledge of specific datasets, domain knowledge** and **ability to apply statistical analysis using available software tools and packages** are skills that are often specific to the TRE or project in which one works. Such skills require context-specific training whereas **TRE literacy** and **knowledge of legal obligations** have broader applicability. And although respondents reported limited proficiency in **knowledge of standard models, ontologies & vocabularies** this skill did not rank as highly used nor specific to sensitive data.

Analysis of skill gaps by career stage indicated that **TRE literacy** consistently appeared in the top five gaps for all stages, while **knowledge of standard models, ontologies & vocabularies**, and **understanding how to write code for data curation** were more prominent for mid and established career respondents. **Knowledge of legal obligations** was less of a skill gap for more established staff. Numbers are relatively low in these breakdowns, so findings should be interpreted with caution.

Thinking about yourself, select up to five skills you feel least well-equipped with for your current role.
Broken down by career stage:

| Established Career |
|---|---|---|
| Top 5 responses (number of responses) | Top 5 responses (number of responses) | Top 5 responses (number of responses) |
| Awareness of and ability to interpret data within its external and contextual influences (5) | Knowledge of specific datasets (8) | Ability to apply statistical analyses using available software tools and packages (6) |
| Understanding of how terminology is used within a certain context (4) | Knowledge of standard data models, ontologies, and vocabularies (e.g., OMOP, DPV, ODRL) (7) | Knowledge of standard data models, ontologies, and vocabularies (e.g., OMOP, DPV, ODRL) (4) |
| Understanding of TRE/SDE infrastructure literacy (4) | Domain knowledge (7) | Ability to apply AI tools in data curation, with an understanding of their value and limitations (4) |
| Knowledge of specific datasets (4) | Understanding of changes in technology that can affect methodologies (6) | Understanding of how to write code for data curation (applying domain knowledge to programming) (3) |
| Ability to understand what researchers need to get out of the data (4) | Understanding of TRE/SDE infrastructure literacy (5) | Understanding of TRE/SDE infrastructure literacy (3) |
| Ability to ask for help (4) | Time/Task management (for own work or that of a team) (5) | Knowledge of organisational processes and standards (e.g., ISO27001) (3) |

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix [1.16](#), [1.17](#), [1.18](#))

When analysing the survey responses further to explore co-occurrences of (1) most important skills, (2) skills unique to sensitive data, and (3) least well-equipped skills, **domain knowledge**, **knowledge of legal obligations**, and **understanding the anonymisation process** emerged as the most commonly cited skills across these categories. Numbers are again low, so caution is advised. ([See appendix 1.19](#))

Taken together, the findings presented thus far indicate no single clear priority skill gap. **TRE literacy** emerges across career stages as a common skill gap, while **knowledge of legal obligations** features strongly when considering skills unique to sensitive data. Other skills such as **domain knowledge** and **knowledge of specific datasets** are project- or TRE-specific.

Focus groups further provided views on what skill should be prioritised for training. There were suggestions including **training on specific software that runs within a TRE**, **training on certain statistical packages**, and **training on a standard process for data access requests**. There was a significant focus in one session on **understanding legal obligations**. Further suggestions were around **training on standard data models**, and **TRE literacy** was flagged as a widely applicable skill, where training should cover the principles of working in TREs, rather than specifics. It was emphasised in the focus groups that *who* the training is for is important, with the different skill requirements at different career levels, and of specific roles with curation and research, being important considerations. From this discussion, **TRE literacy** was identified as a suitable priority skill for training, as all users of TREs require a foundational understanding of their operation. The training should address the same core principles for all participants, with content tailored to different levels of experience:

[Training] should be the same. Everyone should have the same knowledge, the same methods of using the data, and understanding it, and knowing what they can and can't do.

Taking into account both the survey and focus group data, **TRE literacy** is considered a priority skill for the development of training. This is due to its centrality to the curation of sensitive data, its persistence as a skill gap across career stages, and its broad applicability when training focuses on foundational principles rather than platform-specific details. High-impact skills such as **knowledge of legal obligations** can be woven into TRE literacy training, with content tailored to career stage and role relevance.

Training requirements

To better understand training requirements, the survey asked of the skill gaps identified, which skills could people improve on their own, and which they would require additional support to improve.

Which of these skills do you expect to improve by yourself?			
	Respondents	Respondents	
Knowledge of specific datasets	7	9	Understanding of TRE/SDE infrastructure literacy
Time/Task management (for own work or that of a team)	6	8	Ability to understand what researchers need to get out of the data
Knowledge of standard data models, ontologies, and vocabularies (e.g., OMOP, DPV, ODRL)	6	7	Ability to apply statistical analyses using available software tools and packages
Ability to ask for help	4	6	Understanding of how to write code for data curation (applying domain knowledge to programming)
Domain knowledge	4	6	Ability to structure data curation work so that it is reproducible, transparent, and reusable
Ability to build trust with clients/researchers	3	6	Knowledge of legal obligations (e.g., GDPR, disclosure control)
Understanding of how to ask questions of data that help in addressing research aims	3	6	Understanding of changes in technology that can affect methodologies
Ability to create a searchable data catalogue	3	6	Awareness of and ability to interpret data within its external and contextual influences
Understanding of programming concepts (knowing languages, able to learn new languages)	3	5	Knowledge of specific datasets
Understanding of how to combine data from different sources and formats/types for use by researchers	3	5	Domain knowledge
Ability to apply statistical analyses using available software tools and packages	3	4	Ability to create a searchable data catalogue
Ability to apply AI tools in data curation, with an understanding of their value and limitations	3	4	Knowledge of organisational processes and standards (e.g., ISO27001)
Understanding of anonymisation processes	3	4	Ability to do disclosure checks (also known as output checking)
Knowledge of legal obligations (e.g., GDPR, disclosure control)	3	4	Understanding of researchers' methods
Understanding of how terminology is used within a certain context	3	4	Knowledge of standard data models, ontologies, and vocabularies (e.g., OMOP, DPV, ODRL)
Awareness of and ability to interpret data within its external and contextual influences	3		

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix [1.20](#), [1.21](#))

Among the skills identified as most needing additional support, **TRE literacy**, **knowledge of legal obligations**, and the **ability to structure data curation work so that it is reproducible, transparent, and reusable** were consistently highlighted. **TRE literacy**, in particular, was frequently reported as an area where participants would benefit from additional training and also appears across career stages. **Knowledge of legal obligations** and **structuring reproducible workflows** were also noted as important areas for support, though they were cited by fewer respondents as gaps in current capability. Some of these skills, such as **ability to apply statistical analyses using available software tools and packages** and understanding **how to write code for data curation**, are highly context-specific, while others, including **understanding researcher needs** and **awareness of and ability to interpret data within contextual influence**, combine technical and professional capabilities. Participants also noted that **understanding of changes in technology that can affect methodologies** could change quite rapidly, meaning training could become quickly outdated.

Comparison of Skills Needing Additional Training vs. Least Equipped Skills

(See appendix 1.22)

Further analyses of skill gaps requiring additional support across career stages revealed that **TRE literacy** ranked in the top 5 at each career stage, while **knowledge of legal obligations**, and **ability to structure data curation work so that it is reproducible, transparent and reusable** varied. This lends weight to **TRE literacy** as a priority skills gap due to its wide applicability. It is worth noting, however, that a comparison of most important skills and those least well-equipped shows that **TRE literacy** is not as frequently cited as some other skills.

Comparison of Most Important vs. Least Equipped Skills

(See appendix 1.23)

On balance, the evidence supports prioritising **TRE literacy** as a candidate for generalisable training. This reflects its centrality to sensitive data curation, its identification as a cross-career skill gap, clear demand for additional support, and its applicability across different TREs when grounded in foundational principles rather than system-specific detail. To manage the potential mismatch between perceived importance and training need, foundational **TRE literacy** training should integrate other high-impact skills—such as knowledge of legal obligations—tailored by career stage and role relevance. Legal obligations, for example, emerge as particularly important for early-career staff, while more established staff may benefit from reinforcement rather than intensive training.

Training access & barriers

Having explored the skill gaps of people who curate sensitive data, we wanted to explore the training that people have had, and what is available to them. Doing so means we can decide what training might be needed, and how to design our intervention.

We asked respondents what prior formal training supports the skills they need in their data curation work. The findings suggest that entry into sensitive data curation typically draws on university-based education.

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix 1.24)

Is training available?

We also explored the availability of training within respondents' current roles. Analysis by career stage suggests that formal training is more frequently accessible to early career staff, whereas informal and experiential learning predominates at more established stages. Notably, only three respondents across all career stages described access to extensive formal training.

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix [1.25](#), [1.26](#), [1.27](#))

Focus group participants described the types of training currently available. Most referenced mandatory governance and compliance training (e.g., GDPR), typically delivered organisation-wide and not tailored to the specific requirements of sensitive data curation. In one well-resourced TRE, this was supplemented by ISO standards and cyber security training more directly relevant to secure environments, alongside funding support for staff to undertake coding courses. Some participants reported access to Safe Researcher Training (SRT); however, this provision is primarily designed for researchers accessing TREs rather than for curation staff. Across discussions, participants identified a notable gap in training focused specifically on anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques, as well as risk assessment in sensitive data contexts.

How is training delivered?

We asked what format training was provided in, with self-led online training being the most widespread, followed by in-house training and the informal learning done through networks of colleagues. Less frequently cited were external courses, conference participation, university-led training, and engagement with communities of practice.

What formats is this training available in? Select all that apply

(Numbers displayed in parentheses refer to response count; See appendix 1.28)

A focus group participant discussed how self-led online learning was well-liked by the data curators they manage as it allowed them to work through problems that came up in their workflow, without having to take a more structured course. In this instance, the organisation allowed this freedom and there was sufficient time to do this, but this might not always be the case. The early key informant interviews mentioned the role of networks such as the UK TRE Community and the Scottish Safe Haven Network in helping people develop their curation skills through knowledge sharing forums and meet ups. One participant said they had ‘a really good community that if we have issues or we've got questions about a particular dataset, that community is just there’.

Our focus groups also reported the prevalence of informal learning from peers, highlighting its appropriateness when it is related to TRE- or project-specific skills like domain knowledge, knowledge of datasets, and knowledge of certain software. Nevertheless, it was argued that a strong foundation in data curation was required for this informal learning to be effective. Focus groups highlighted that historically, informal learning has been necessary due to the need for data curation predated formal recognition of the profession. Participants also noted that the historical lack of recognition meant training was often not included in organisational budgets. While progress has been made, gaps remain, including the lack of a granular skills framework and limited awareness of training opportunities relevant to sensitive data curation.

Funding

When it comes to how training is funded, a plurality of respondents at each career stage indicated that their organisation pays for their training. However, this seems to reduce at later career stages, with either self-funding or no funding reported.

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix [1.29](#), [1.30](#), [1.31](#))

Focus groups discussed funding, indicating the context in which they operated had an impact on what was available. One participant highlighted that because they had paying customers using their TRE there was an expectation that they had a well-trained workforce, so they ‘always [found] budgetary funding to provide training for the team’. Elsewhere, training budgets were not available from the core funding from the NHS or university, meaning they had to be top sliced from research grants, and were often insufficient.

Barriers to training

Respondents were asked to identify barriers to training and rank their severity. While limited time during working hours was the most commonly reported barrier, a lack of suitable courses was ranked as the most significant barrier.

Please rank the barriers you have chosen

Scored: 1st = 5 points, 5th = 1 point

(See appendix [1.32](#), [133](#))

Focus group discussions explored these issues. Participants highlighted a lack of time to train was a function of the prioritisation of getting work done on limited budgets. It was raised that the lack of recognition of data curation as a skilled profession, in need of dedicated training, meant the time to train was not budgeted for. Another participant raised the idea that a culture of taking time to train is not present in some workplaces, despite policies being in place.

The widespread recognition of a lack of suitable training was explored in focus groups. Participants explained this in two ways: first, people often did not know which courses were appropriate for their or their staff's specific context and prior experience; second, many available courses were not directly relevant to the curation of sensitive data, with one participant noting 'it's too much choice and not enough choice at the same time'

Sixteen percent of respondents were unsure of what skills were needed. This speaks to the still nascent nature of the profession where a codified skills framework has not yet been developed and/or widely adopted. There was a strong call – 74% of survey respondents – for a structured skills framework, and this sentiment was echoed by focus group participants.

(Numbers displayed refer to response count; See appendix 1.34)

While structural barriers were cited just twice (one for disability/accessibility and one ‘prefer not to say’), focus groups raised the importance of catering for neurodivergent staff, and addressing the potential for ageism, with some employers not considering that older workers would still like to develop their skills.

Any training needs to directly address, or take into account, the barriers described above so that as many people as possible are able to take advantage of what is offered. Suggestions for how to do this are discussed below.

Future training needs

Survey respondents highlighted AI as an emerging area of skills and training needs within TREs, with 24% (n=21) of participants specifically mentioning it. Responses generally fell into two themes. The first focused on using AI within data curation workflows, including understanding AI tools and processes, interpreting model outputs, and applying AI for tasks such as code generation for data curation. Some respondents also expressed interest in understanding how to support researchers using and applying AI to the data as part of their research.

The second theme focused on responsible and appropriate use of AI, particularly in the context of sensitive data. Key concerns included understanding legal and governance limitations, risks associated with privacy and disclosure, and assessing when AI outputs are appropriate for research purposes. Respondents expressed interest in developing skills to check outputs, carry out disclosure assessments, and detect or challenge inappropriate uses of AI, as well as understanding the broader social and environmental implications of AI deployment.

Focus groups reinforced these themes, highlighting that while AI is increasingly being adopted in research workflows, TREs are not yet fully equipped to support it safely. Participants emphasized the need for AI awareness rather than training on specific AI tools, including the ability to understand risks, interpret outputs, and communicate effectively about AI within TREs. Concerns were raised about potential misuse, hallucination of sensitive information, and risks to data

governance, with consensus that AI applications should be tightly controlled, clearly understood, and aligned with organisational policies.

Quotes from participants illustrate these concerns vividly:

I don't want our data fed into an AI. I think that has some fairly significant information governance concerns... about it hallucinating or regurgitating private, secure information back to researchers... I'm extremely sceptical about using it on the data itself, unless it's a very specifically trained model for a very specific purpose that is going to be checked and used in highly restricted ways. I just think in the context of sensitive data, AI is not something that should really be a high priority for a unit.

If we've got really good-quality data, along with the right controls, it probably would work better, but at the moment there's such a lot of high instances of poor data.

Despite these misgivings, there was recognition that AI use in research is likely to grow rapidly. Participants acknowledged:

Whether we like it or not, if [AI is] where the money goes, that's what people are going to be wanting to do their research in... We're just way, way, way behind where it could go and the funders, it's easy money for them, doing massive amounts of analysis very easily and other research is going to go out the window... I think it's quite dangerous really.

Taken together, these findings highlight an emerging priority within the wider TRE literacy agenda: building AI awareness so that professionals can understand the risks, limitations, and appropriate uses of AI within TREs, support researchers responsibly, and safeguard data security and research integrity.

What should training look like?

Focus groups considered what makes training effective and appropriate. Participants emphasised that the format of training should vary with the topic being taught, with broad agreement that self-directed online learning is effective for delivering content that accommodates other commitments and can be made widely accessible. It was agreed that both principles of **TRE literacy** and **knowledge of legal obligations** could be taught in this way. This modular content lends itself to providing training at different levels for people with different experience much like the Software

Carpenteries, that offers beginner and intermediate training. However, the lack of in-person training was seen as a negative, as participants felt working with other people is more engaging and impactful. Several people advocated for workshops where people with knowledge and practical understanding of the skill in question can support participants. They highlighted that this is an engaging and practical training method as people can troubleshoot their own scenarios, rather than it being abstract: 'It's really good if it's in a workshop environment and you're getting people to talk to each other and not just listen.' Mentoring, practical workshops and surgeries were suggested as effective ways to teach domain knowledge. For technical skills, peer-to-peer training was discussed, similar to how code review works. While likely very practical and effective, these sorts of training would be hard to deliver en masse due to the need for peers with knowledge of context-specific skills. Finally, the idea of using a LLM to help people was floated: 'We'll dump everything that we want to tell people and teach them, and then that's all you do. You just interact with a bot and ask it questions. "Am I allowed to do this?" "How would I code that?" The bot will tell you'. However, another participant pointed out that currently there is not enough training content available, but this might be something that could be useful once the profession is more established. Contemplating these arguments, a 'flipped classroom' model was deemed appropriate, combining online foundational learning with applied in-person sessions to support flexibility and effective skill development. A benefit of this approach is that the general principles of TRE literacy or other skills can be applied to the specific context that people are working in.

Staff motivation and organisational buy-in was considered by the focus groups, framed around a 'carrot or stick' dichotomy. It was argued that pitching training as mandatory or compliance would ensure completion but might not engender engagement. The idea of a 'driver's licence' for a particular TRE was floated, meaning people would be required to gain this before using the TRE. There was enthusiasm for voluntary certification, seen as a positive for someone's reputation and support their career development, and in line with the IT sector.

Certification from different providers is a norm for IT, so I think matching that in terms of data curation, courses, skills, etc... certified by professional bodies.

Embedding training into performance management tasks was seen as an excellent way of motivating staff to take part, and to encourage organisational buy-in. This can also support recognition of training, with the possibility of improved funding.

Next steps

This work provides an evidence-base and understanding of where [early action is feasible](#) and where [broader sector involvement is needed](#). The immediate priority is to develop a modular, open source ‘train the trainer’ pilot in TRE literacy with a curriculum focused on core principles, rather than TRE specific processes.

A key element of the next phase will be working with stakeholders to encourage uptake of the wider recommendations emerging from this review. Funders, training providers, and TREs/SDes/Safe Havens have an important role in progressing the remaining priority skill areas and addressing challenges; and we support this by sharing evidence, convening conversations, and highlighting practical routes for adoption.

Limitations

The world of sensitive data research is fast-moving and remarkably diverse, and this work offers a snapshot within it. Focused on sensitive data curation, we’ve captured a small (yet important) specific slice of wider data stewardship, with participation weighted toward established professionals working with health data; and limited input from early-career researchers and professionals based in Wales.

While our findings reflect current perspectives, the landscape is evolving quickly (for example, with the advent of the Health Data Research Service) and skill requirements, training provision, and infrastructure are likely to change over times as TREs increasingly adopt cloud-native and federated architectures. In exploring training and skills needs, we aimed to identify commonalities in requirements across TREs, disciplines, and data types, but recognise the need to balance generalisable findings with context-specific realities (such as the diversity of legal and governance frameworks across TREs and data types including GDPR, national statutory frameworks, consent-based cohorts, and institutional agreements, etc.)

Methodology

Our research was designed to capture perspectives on skills and training needs for the curation of sensitive data. This qualitative study was conducted over the course of 2025, involving seven key informant interviews with people highly experienced in the curation of sensitive data in a range of contexts, a survey aimed at those in the UK who curate sensitive data, and three follow-up focus groups that explored the themes of skill gaps and training access/barriers in more depth. First, we (the research team) drew on our networks to set up interviews with seven key informants, targeting a range of different settings so that we could understand the nuances of the UK sensitive data curation landscape. We asked them to define sensitive data and the types of data they work with, explain the division of labour in their data curation processes, list the skills needed for the curation of sensitive data, discuss the skill gaps that exist and the reason for these gaps, and outline what training is available and what barriers there are to staff taking up this training. We also asked about how things might change in the future and about career development for those who curate data. These findings were analysed by the research team and led to the development of an anonymous online survey that was able to capture the broad range of experiences of data curators of sensitive data. The survey was disseminated through HDR UK networks and ran over the summer, garnering 92 partial responses and 87 full responses. Three focus groups ran in November to further probe themes from the survey, namely the prioritisation of skills to deliver, and the form our training should take.

Ethics

Approval for the study was granted by University of Southampton's ethics committee (ERGO number: 100680).

Prior to interviews and focus groups, potential participants were provided with an information sheet that provided details about the aims of the research, the interview process (such as audio/video recording and transcription), confidentiality and anonymisation processes, and data storage and archiving. Participants completed an email consent process. Interviews and focus groups were transcribed, and transcripts pseudonymised and retained for archiving in a University of Southampton data repository.

Recruitment and sample

The research team identified a long list of potential 'key informants' who would be able to provide deep insight into the diverse sensitive data curation landscape. We then shortlisted in order to select a spread of experience and data types and invited them to an online interview via email. We conducted seven interviews. Table x shows selected attributes.

Table 1. Key informant interview participants.

	Role	Organisation Type	Data types	Location
1	Senior data scientist	Research institute	Health	England
2	Infrastructure engineer	University/TRE	Health	Scotland
3	TRE director	University/TRE	Social	England
4	TRE director	TRE	Health	Scotland
4	Operational lead TRE			
5	Infrastructure manager	University/TRE	Health	Scotland
6	Head of infrastructure	Research council	Social	UK
7	Data science lead	Private sector research	Genomic	England

The survey was distributed via HDR UK networks including, for example, the UK TRE Community, Secure Access Data Professionals (SDAP) and SDE and Scottish Safe Haven networks. We intended to recruit as many curators of sensitive data as possible, with the networks well placed to reach people working with sensitive data across the four nations.

We achieved 92 partial and 87 full responses to the survey. There is no data on the size of the workforce that curates sensitive data so we are unable to comment on the significance of this sample. We did not collect any demographic data, but some statistics on career stage, organisation type and responsibilities feature in Table 2.

Table 2. Survey respondents.

Career stage	Phase 1 - Trainee	3
	Phase 2 - Early Career	23
	Phase 3 - Mid/recognised	40
	Phase 4 - Established	26
Sector	Academic	59
	Government	17
	Nonprofit/charity	10
	NHS	8
	Private sector/industry	4

Focus groups were recruited via an expression of interest form, distributed through relevant networks. This received 33 responses, and we selected based on career stage and a diversity of organisational contexts. In the end, very few early career.

Table 3 shows selected attributes from focus group participants.

Table 3. Focus group participants.

	Role	Organisation Type	Data types	Location	Career Stage
1	Data steward	University/TRE	Multiple	England	Mid/recognised
2	Data warehousing manager	NHS Trust	NHS/Health	England	Established
3	Data manager	Data controller	Health	England	Mid/recognised
4	TRE Manager	University/TRE	Health	Scotland	Established
5	Information analyst	TRE	Health	Scotland	Mid/recognised
6	Head of data service	University/TRE	Health	England	Established
7	Data manager	TRE	Social science	England	Mid/recognised
8	Technical data engineer	University/TRE	Multiple	Scotland	Mid/recognised
9	Info governance lead	University/TRE	Multiple	Wales	Established
10	User of TRE	Third sector	Multiple	England	Established
11	User of TRE	User	Health	England	Early
12	Information governance	Research institute	Health	England	Mid/recognised
13	Infrastructure lead	TRE	Health	UK	Established
14	Data Scientist	Research institute	Health	England	Early
15	Data specialist	Research institute	Multiple	England	Established
16	Medical professional	University/TRE	Health	Scotland	Established

Key informant interviews

The interviews were designed to last between 45 minutes and 1 hour and were conducted online following a semi-structured topic guide. We asked participants about details of their work in the curation of sensitive data in order to contextualise their responses. We then asked for definitions of data curation and sensitive data, the skills needed for data curation work, any skill gaps that exist for them or their team, the reasons for any gaps, and the training that is (and is not) available. We asked about challenges to effective data curation and finally, any future skills requirements that are likely to arise.

Focus groups

We ran three focus groups which were designed to last for around 2 hours and were also conducted online. The first two were with a range of staff and public users of TREs, with one focused on trying to prioritise skill gaps and what requires training and the other focused on access and barriers to training. The final focus group was with more senior or experienced staff, who we asked about both topic areas. The topic guide for focus groups is openly available (see [Data Availability](#)). Participants were invited to answer individually and then given the opportunity to discuss each other's responses. While we purposefully constrained the scope of the focus group through the questions we posed, we did not try to force a consensus positions. Rather, we sought data that provided context and depth to the themes from the survey. Due to the small numbers of participants and the high level of contextual information, we are not able to effectively anonymise the transcripts.

Data analysis

After transcription of the audio recording, interviews and focus groups were coded in Atlas.ti, qualitative data analysis (QDA) software. We first coded to broad thematic and descriptive codes reflecting the interview and focus group themes. These included information on participants and their contexts, skills, skill gaps, reasons for skill gaps, access and barriers to training, and future challenges. Later, more fine-grained coding captured the themes that emerged relating to skills, skill gaps, reasons for gaps, and training. These codes enabled us to analyse and understand the existing skills and training landscape and allowed us to prioritise the skills we are going to develop training for. The list of thematic codes are openly available ([see Data Availability](#)).

Quantitative survey results were downloaded as a csv file and read into R. For each item, rows with missing values were first removed. Then the number of instances of each response was counted and the percentage of respondents who gave the response was calculated and plotted. Tidyverse functions were used throughout data cleaning and analysis.

Data availability

Data and code supporting this study are openly accessible under a CC BY 4.0 license.

The anonymised survey data are available from the University of Southampton repository (DOI: [10.5258/SOTON/D3811](https://doi.org/10.5258/SOTON/D3811)), alongside the topic guide for key informant interviews and focus groups, and the thematic codes for qualitative data.

Analysis code for the Sensitive Data Skills Survey is available via Zenodo (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18378101](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18378101)). Qualitative focus group and informant interview data are not shared because effective anonymisation could not be achieved without compromising participant confidentiality.

Appendix

(1.1)

(1.2)

In the plots below, we have used blue to indicate skills that are predominantly technical, and yellow for skills that are predominantly professional, or 'soft'.

(1.3)

(1.4)

(1.5)

What types or formats of data do you work with? Select all that apply.

(1.6)

Phase 2 - Early: responsibilities

(1.7)

(1.8)

(1.9)

(1.10)

(1.11)

(1.12)

(1.13)

(1.14)

(1.15)

Thinking about yourself, select up to five skills you feel least well-equipped with for your current role.

(1.16)

Phase 2 - Early: least well-equipped

(1.17)

(1.18)

(1.19)

(1.20)

(1.21)

(1.22)

(1.23)

Comparison of Most Important vs. Least Equipped Skills

(1.24)

(1.25)

(1.26)

(1.27)

(1.28)

(1.29)

(1.30)

(1.31)

(1.32)

(1.33)

(1.34)

